

Voice Interfaces for Library Accessibility: Challenges Identified by Academic Librarians

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the potential for using a voice interface to improve access to reading materials for students who are blind. Students who are blind face many barriers to higher education, including access to reading materials due to graphical library database interfaces that are often not designed to be accessible. This paper reports findings from semi-structured, open-ended interviews with 25 academic librarians with experience serving students who are blind. Themes emerging from the interviews included challenges in developing a voice interface for accessing library materials in terms of the academic library context, user behavior, and voice interface technology. For the academic library context, the challenges included cost, technical expertise, and spatial limitations. For user behavior, the challenges involved developing complex search queries using a voice interface. For voice interface technology, librarians identified the lack of interconnectivity among library databases, the difficulty in presenting search query results via voice, and the potential for bias as challenges. These findings demonstrate broad interest in such a voice interface among academic librarians and provide guideposts for steering the design of such a voice interface.

KEYWORDS

Academic Libraries; Students Who Are Blind; Accessibility; Assistive Technologies; Voice Interfaces

INTRODUCTION

Educational equity for people with disabilities is a critical societal challenge. Unfortunately, achieving true equity and inclusion in education remains elusive. There is a substantial gap in educational opportunities and attainment among people with a visual disability versus those without. While 34.1% of people aged 21-64 without a visual disability held a bachelor's degree or higher, only 16.5% of people aged 21-64 with a visual disability held a bachelor's degree or higher (Disability Statistics, n.d.). Students who are blind face many barriers, including challenges in accessing reading materials. While text-to-speech has made it easier to interact with reading materials, the process of searching for these materials continues to present challenges, as library databases often fail to consider accessibility. The goal of this paper is to explore the perspectives of academic librarians with experience serving students who are blind on the potential for the development of a voice interface to access library materials.

For the purposes of this study, "academic librarians" refers to librarians working in a post-secondary institution of higher learning. Further, "students who are blind" refers to students who are blind or who have low vision, using the people-first language preferred by the first author, who is a member of this community. Finally, "voice interface to access library materials" refers to the use of a voice-based digital assistant that can provide an audio-based way to search for reading materials. The primary research question answered by this study is: "What challenges do academic librarians identify related to developing a voice interface to access library materials for students who are blind?"

This paper begins by exploring some of the issues within the current educational system affecting students who are blind, including an overview of accessibility in educational environments in general, as well as the pivotal role of reading material accessibility in education. Methods involved 25 interviews with academic librarians. Themes related to these librarians' perspectives on challenges related to using a voice interface to access library materials are presented and connected back to the relevant research literature. The conclusion explores the potential contributions of this work both to theory and to practice.

BACKGROUND

Prior studies have focused on how academic libraries can improve information services for students who are blind, demonstrating some progress toward boosting awareness of accessibility issues. Previous research on information services for students with disabilities can be characterized with respect to three threads. The first thread is conducting case studies in academic libraries presenting best practices. For example, based on the site visits to 8 academic libraries, Samson (2011) found that there was no consistent approach or set of best practices to service students with disabilities across the participating libraries. While case studies are prominent methods for accessibility research in library settings, this approach tends to focus on checking the boxes, as a result, the findings may not reveal meaningful accessibility issues and challenges that can be used in other libraries (Kimura, 2018).

The second thread is to conduct a survey with librarians and administrator to identify ways to improve information services. Based on 72 responses from an online survey, Potnis and Mallary (2021) identified five mechanisms representing modified work practice that could enhance the quality of information services offered to library users with disabilities. Tripathi and Shukla (2014) compared the websites of 60 academic libraries across India, the UK, the US, and Canada to find out how assistive technology had been used to meet the information needs of visually challenged students.

The third thread is to study people who are blind to better understand their needs and behavior. For instance, Babu and Xie (2017) collected data on non-visual interaction experiences with a digital collection from 15 blind participants using questionnaire, pre-interview, think-aloud, and post-interview methods. They identified five categories of design problems that prevent blind users from using the digital library effectively. Further, research on voice interfaces has demonstrated the need to avoid and mitigate bias in the use of these systems (Bilal & Barfield, 2021; Yi et al., 2020).

METHODS

This paper reports findings from a portion of an interview study with academic librarians with experience providing library materials to student who are blind or have low vision. Librarians were recruited via emails to listservs. Participating librarians were compensated with a \$50 gift card. The study was approved by the researchers' Institutional Review Board. Inclusion criteria included working full-time as academic librarians in the US and having experience serving or providing library materials to students who are blind or have low vision. Many of the participating librarians forwarded our research call to their colleagues and professional contacts. The interview instrument build upon an earlier pilot study involving four academic librarians (Day & Fleischmann, 2020). Of the 28 participants in the overall study, 25 were asked and answered questions about the possibility of using voice interfaces to access library materials; this paper focuses on this subset of questions. Interviews were conducted via Zoom between October 2021 and January 2022. Interviews were recorded and then transcribed using Otter.ai.

Among the 25 participants who were asked questions related to a voice interface, three work as accessibility librarians, six work as access services librarians, two work as instructional librarians, three work as scholarly communications librarians, five work as student success librarians, four work as subject specialists, and two work as user service librarians. In terms of the Carnegie Classifications, two work at institutions where the bachelor's degree is the highest awarded degree, seven work at institutions where the master's degree is the highest awarded degree, and 16 work at institutions where the doctoral degree is the highest awarded degree. For geography, seven work in the Midwestern US, seven work in the Northern US, five work in the Southern US, and six work in the Western US.

After the data collection phase concluded, two independent coders on the research team reviewed the portion of each transcript pertaining to the use of AI in libraries to assist students who are blind to locate and use reading materials. Thematic analysis was used to identify common experiences and sentiments expressed by participants. The independent coders discussed results for validity and created themes and sub-themes encapsulating the most impactful results. This paper reports results related to challenges to using voice interfaces.

RESULTS

Overall, the participating academic librarians expressed a strong interest in the idea of developing a voice interface to facilitate access to library materials. However, these academic librarians also identified important challenges that must be overcome in developing such a voice interface. Thematic analysis of the portion of the interview transcripts related to challenges to providing access to library materials using a voice interface revealed three main themes. First, participants identified challenges related to the academic library context. Second, they discussed challenges related to user behavior. Third, they noted challenges related to voice interface technology. Overall, these results provide useful feedback from an important stakeholder group, librarians with experience in providing accessible reading materials to students who are blind, about challenges to developing voice interfaces to improve reading material accessibility for students who are blind.

Challenges Related to the Academic Library Context

Several participating academic librarians identified cost as a challenge. For example, a subject specialist noted, "Oh, the first one is financial, financial support for the project or protected time for people to work on the project and to be able to collaborate in the ways that they need to." Thus, cost includes financial commitments as well as librarians' time. A related challenge identified by a student success librarian was the technical expertise needed to develop such a voice interface: "Good programmers in the world go to Google and Amazon and these big corporations...finding people with the right skill set and the right knowledge for the wages that higher education is paying [is a challenge]". Another student success librarian identified privacy as an issue, "An academic library put an Alexa on their counter so that students could ask reference questions...and it became a privacy issue...libraries tend to pride themselves on being good stewards of privacy." Similarly, an instructional librarian asked, "Where in the library would this happen? So that the student has privacy but is also not interrupting other work that's

happening in the library.” Finally, a scholarly communications librarian noted, “one problem with this accessibility conversation is a lot of librarians have never seen, used, or really particularly understood how a screen reader works or how people who are blind or have disabilities might be using a screen reader. And so, I think that having that knowledge would really be...the first step.” Thus, librarians’ lack of understanding of and experiences with assistive technology is another important challenge in developing a voice access to improve access to reading materials for students who are blind.

Challenges Related to User Behavior

Some librarians in our study pointed out that the information seeking and searching behaviors of the user play a critical role in determining system effectiveness. A student success librarian noted, “If using verbal commands is just a shortcut for any user to obtain information, it could lead to a superficial level of searching.” Implementing advanced search features and Boolean searches using a voice interface in an intuitive way could be challenging. An access services librarian noted, “Students...will just accept the first types of sources that they encounter, and not necessarily continue down the path to find the best types of research sources for themselves.” These insights point to a possibility of decreased engagement on the user’s part which has the potential to produce less than fruitful results.

Challenges Related to Voice Interface Technology

Several participating librarians also identified challenges related to the voice interface technology itself. A student success librarian raised the issue of interconnectivity with databases, “Our databases...are not super streamlined...clunky...the user experience is not amazing. And we haven’t quite figured out how to do that better.” Similarly, an accessibility librarian noted, “I think the, the challenge would be, how is the information being returned to the user? The user’s using a screen reader, they know how to navigate the results page. And if that’s marked up and organized, well, then it can be successful...But if the person is using Siri, or something like that...how to how have a voice interface that would present the findings seems like the challenging part.” Thus, delivering search results in a meaningful way using a voice interface could be challenging. An access services librarian raised issues with voice recognition, “But for the user, it’s going to be the same frustration that anybody has working with Alexa right now, right? That everything you say is not necessarily interpreted by the program as accurate, and it can be frustrating. And if it’s frustrating, then some students might easily turn away and not attempt to continue with their access, or that they will simply accept what they’ve found with their limited attempts, and just go with what’s good enough, as opposed to finding the right source for what they were searching for.” Similarly, an accessibility librarian explained, “Definitely there’s bias in voice recognition software, especially with perhaps non-native English speakers...that can be frustrating.” Thus, these technical challenges would need to be addressed.

DISCUSSION

Three factors distinguish this study from previous studies on accessibility in academic libraries. First, this study investigated a particular technology – a voice interface to access library materials – to improve accessibility for students who are blind. While other studies have focused on assistive technologies, such technologies have limited adoption given the narrow audiences to which they are typically aimed, which limits access to these technologies. This paper focuses on a voice interface because this technology has great potential for offering an AI-based solution that could transform the experience of students who are blind in academic libraries, and which could be an adaptable and ubiquitous solution that has the potential to benefit all students.

Second, rather than a using case study or survey, this paper reports findings from interviews with academic librarians who have experience serving students who are blind. This enabled us to gather rich data about their perspectives, ideas, and opinions about what a voice interface might offer and what obstacles they may face if they decide to implement such a system in their library. Although participating librarians’ job titles and responsibilities varied, they shared rich perspectives on how a voice interface could be designed, developed, and deployed.

Third, the set of interview questions asked during the study resulted on findings that connect to and build upon prior research. For example, Samson (2011) recommended that libraries examine improvements which could be made to the physical space as well as the services provided by the library with the intention of increasing accessibility. This broad but important recommendation encourages opening a dialog to actively identify specific accessibility issues and implement solutions to address them.

The findings of this study provide more specificity about modifications to the physical space of libraries that would be needed to accommodate the use of voice interfaces. For example, spaces would need to be created to allow library users to interact with voice interfaces without interrupting other library users, while also helping to preserve the privacy of users when interacting with voice interfaces. Babu and Xie (2017) examined digital collection search challenges in terms of traditional text-based searching. Similarly, Tripathi and Shukla (2014) focused on visual and tactile ways to enhance reading, plus text-to-speech interfaces that simply passively read text to the user without allowing users to dynamically interact with the text. While traditional search methods have challenges rooted in webpage design, voice interface technology is new in comparison and may present a better alternative to

conventional methods of search. Thus, this topic merits further study. This paper takes the first step in that direction by identifying a key stakeholder group and asking questions which bring to light broad stroke issues which must be considered in future implementation attempts. Voice interfaces need to be designed to be robust in supporting a broad range of voices, in terms of factors including but not limited to national origin and disability status. Further, the formulation of queries and the delivery of results when using a voice interface introduce new research challenges worthy of future study.

The challenge of making library resources accessible has been explored in various ways, most of which take either a broad look at accessibility in general or try to explore and make recommendations on a specific piece of the puzzle. Unfortunately, most solutions attempt to mitigate the accessibility challenge by working around an existing architecture. This is the philosophy behind most assistive technology. However, Kimura (2018) points out that digital information is flexible in terms of medium as it only consists of ones and zeros at its core. In short, Kimura points out that the capabilities of technology are evolving rapidly, however the way in which we implement inclusive solutions to equity of access problems remains stagnant. Therefore, catalyzing the beginnings of a conversation around how newer technologies, such as voice interfaces, could play a role in solving persistent accessibility issues is a needed step toward advancing the discussion around universal access. However, based on the findings of this study, limitations in the technology expertise found in libraries can serve as a limiting factor to the degree to which libraries can serve as hubs for innovation. Librarians often do not have sufficient experience with accessible technologies such as screen readers. It is important to remember that librarians are not the only stakeholder affected by this conversation. Potnis and Mallary (2021) point out that libraries are organizations, and function through partnerships with internal and external parties. While we have taken the initial step in exploring challenges to implementing voice interfaces in libraries, it will be important to build on the conversation by involving other stakeholders as well. In addition, it is important to note that this study had some additional limitations which could be addressed in future work enriching this conversation.

This study carries important limitations. First, the sample included in this study, while relatively broad and diverse, is still a relatively small subset of the overall group of academic librarians with experience in serving students who are blind, and does not include librarians who may not be aware of the ways that their library services may serve (or exclude) students who are blind. To address this limitation, a large-scale nationwide survey of academic librarians could be deployed to test the generalizability of the findings of this study. Second, the sample included only academic librarians working within the US. It would be useful to conduct similar studies in other national contexts to provide a cross-cultural perspective. Third, this study only considered the perspectives of academic librarians, and does not directly address the perspectives of students who are blind, or of staff working in disability and accessibility offices. Thus, it would be productive to conduct similar studies with these important stakeholder groups. Finally, this study only involves speculation about the potential challenges and implications of voice interfaces to access library materials. There is a need to conduct user-centered design to design, develop, deploy, and evaluate the effectiveness of such voice interfaces.

CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the results of this study revealed academic librarians' perspectives on the use of a voice interface to access library materials. Librarians described some of the challenges that would need to be overcome to successfully design, develop, and deploy such a voice interface, including challenges related to the academic library context, to the user behavior, and to the voice interface technology. Challenges related to the academic library context included cost, expertise, and space considerations. Further investment in academic libraries is needed to ensure that libraries have both the personnel and resources needed to be technology innovators, rather than just followers, and the space of libraries needs to be adapted to accommodate new technologies with new modes of interaction. Challenges related to user behavior involved the complexity of implementing advanced searching techniques via a voice interface. Further expanding search skills into the K-12 curriculum would be one way to help users to become more sophisticated in how they formulate search queries, whether they are typed or spoken. Challenges related to voice interface technology included interconnectivity of library databases, delivering search results via speech in a meaningful way, and avoiding bias. One potential solution is design voice interfaces that are conversational, making search a more dynamic and collaborative interaction between the user and the search system. Thus, the findings from this study point out some promising directions for future innovation at the intersection of academic libraries, students who are blind, and assistive technology. All students stand to benefit from the design of a voice interface to access library materials, but such a system must be designed around the constraints and affordances of the context of academic libraries and the needs and values of students.

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